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**Report on Algorithmic Changes and Memory
Optimisation for Heterogeneous Systems in
Plasma-PEPSC Codes**

WP5: Accelerated Plasma Simulations on Heterogeneous Systems

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Executive Summary

This document provides insight into the current state of porting efforts for the Plasma-PEPSC codes toward using accelerator hardware such as graphics processing units (GPUs). It summarizes state-of-the-art techniques for accelerator programming, porting strategies from CPU to accelerators and usage of multiple GPUs. One focus is the use of heterogeneous memory when using accelerators, showcasing some of the libraries provided by Plasma-PEPSC members for memory management on heterogeneous devices.

Although this report documents work in progress, it is evident that almost all Plasma-PEPSC codes are ready for use with GPU accelerators in production on EuroHPC systems. We thus are confident to be able to present regular updates on GPU performance within the project.

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1 Introduction

This report provides an in-depth examination of the adaptation of Plasma-PEPSC codes to accelerators and heterogeneous memory systems, with a focus on utilizing advanced EuroHPC high-performance computing (HPC) resources. By leveraging cutting-edge GPU technology and complex memory hierarchies, the report addresses the challenges and opportunities associated with achieving scalable and efficient plasma simulations.

The report begins by offering a comprehensive background on the evolution and current state of accelerator hardware, programming models, and heterogeneous memory systems. It explores the transformation of GPUs from specialized graphics processors to powerful tools for scientific simulations. The discussion highlights the critical need for adapting and the simulation codes to these cutting-edge technologies to optimize performance and scalability on modern HPC platforms.

It then delves into the current state of implementation, examining the progress made in porting and optimizing key Plasma-PEPSC codes. Detailed analyses of individual codes provide insights into their specific advancements, challenges, and areas for future improvement, showcasing the collaborative effort to overcome technical bottlenecks.

An exploration of GPU acceleration strategies follows, presenting the methods and tools employed to harness the full potential of GPUs. This includes a discussion of programming interfaces, multi-GPU communication techniques, and lessons learned in optimizing data movement and computation for heterogeneous systems. The section emphasizes the importance of efficient resource utilization to achieve high-performance outcomes.

The report also investigates performance optimization strategies, focusing on critical path analysis, mixed-precision arithmetic, and enhanced data locality. By examining these methodologies, the discussion sheds light on how refinements in computational processes contribute to improved scalability and throughput, particularly in large-scale simulations.

The complexities of heterogeneous memory systems are addressed in a dedicated section, which highlights the challenges of managing memory hierarchies in GPU-accelerated environments. Tools and frameworks like LLAMA are introduced as innovative solutions for optimizing memory layouts and minimizing data transfer overheads, offering practical insights into achieving efficient memory utilization.

Finally, the report concludes with a summary of achievements and ongoing challenges, reflecting on the lessons learned and setting the stage for future advancements. It emphasizes the significance of these developments for the broader field of plasma simulations and high-performance computing, paving the way for exascale readiness and next-generation simulation capabilities.

2 Background on Accelerators and Heterogeneous Memory

Using hardware accelerators in addition to standard central processing units (CPU) for either specific tasks, as a general purpose support or even as a replacement for most of the tasks usually performed by the CPU has been around for decades.

Here, we specifically focus on accelerators used in scientific computing with a focus on accelerating numerical tasks. In recent years, the increased use of machine learning in connection with classical numerical tasks predominantly used for scientific simulations has broadened the spectrum of accelerator applications in scientific computing.

Early applications of accelerators included the use of specific numerical co-processors that could execute certain numerical computations faster than standard CPUs [23]. Since the first decade of the century it became apparent that the progress in hardware used for graphics processing was fitting for scientific computing [12], starting a two decade long development in using general purpose graphics processing units (*GPGPU*) for scientific computing now fueling the artificial intelligence revolution. Less prominent, yet in line with increasing parallelism in CPUs, cross-platform programming models [35, 41] and vectorization [31, 8] have seen increasing interest.

Two of the major consequences of this development have been the creation of a variety of programming models, including vendor-based, closed source solutions [24] and open solutions [4, 13, 28] and the rise of deep memory hierarchies [22]. Both developments pose challenges to existing scientific simulation codes, as they usually have to use more than one programming model to run on a variety of state-of-the-art high-performance computer systems and are faced with the difficulties of complex data movement, hiding latencies and optimizing throughput. This has increased the need to optimize codes for specific accelerator hardware and to refactor codes for optimum data locality. As optimization is an additional burden to development teams, it has been observed that utilization of floating point performance in codes is often hampered by high latencies and low bandwidths in accelerator hardware, leading to many codes becoming memory-bound [15, 16, 17].

The major part of this report will focus on GPGPU programming, especially on hardware from either *Nvidia* or *AMD* as the two major competitors in the field. When appropriate, we will refer to alternative subjects. With most of the European high performance computing systems in the Top 10 of supercomputers using accelerators from either Nvidia or AMD, developments for EPI accelerators is mainly deferred to WP2 and reported there.

3 Porting Status and Optimization Potential of the Codes

This section examines the current state of the four codes, detailing their progress in utilizing GPU acceleration and heterogeneous memory. It reviews the specific optimization techniques applied to each code and identifies areas where further improvements are needed.

3.1 BIT

Particle-in-Cell (PIC) Monte Carlo (MC) simulations are crucial for modeling plasma-material interactions, a critical component of fusion energy research due to the complex dynamics and the wide range of spatial and temporal scales involved. These simulations also incorporate atomic and collision processes. BIT1, a 1D3V PIC MC code, simulates

particle trajectories in a field governed by Maxwell’s and Poisson’s equations, enabling the study of plasma behavior with three-dimensional velocity components.

Previous analyses of BIT1 identified performance bottlenecks, particularly in the particle mover function, which calculates particle trajectories and manages the movement of particles between grid cells and MPI ranks [39]. This stage is computationally intensive due to the need to process millions of particles [37]. Efforts have focused on enhancing performance by optimizing BIT1’s computational processes, particularly through asynchronous execution.

BIT1 employs domain decomposition and MPI for parallelization, exchanging information at domain boundaries for tasks such as the smoother and Poisson solver. However, BIT1 currently does not utilize hybrid parallelization techniques, such as MPI+OpenMP or GPU offloading, relying solely on MPI. The code’s data layout stores particle positions and velocities within grid cells, transferring data between lists as particles move. Load imbalances arise in plasma simulations due to uneven particle concentrations across cells, reducing the efficiency of the particle mover function. Efforts to address these challenges aim to improve BIT1’s performance through asynchronous programming and optimization of its most demanding components.

To identify optimal BIT1 porting opportunities, the focus has been on optimizing the particle mover function and analyzing its performance in large-scale plasma simulations. A test case was conducted to simulate neutral particle ionization in an unbounded, unmagnetized plasma, representative of conditions in fusion devices like ITER and DEMO. The scenario included electrons, D^+ ions, and D neutrals, with ionization reducing neutral concentrations over time. The simulation employed a one-dimensional geometry with 100K cells, three plasma species, and 10M particles per species, totaling 30M particles across 200K time steps, excluding the field solver and smoother phases (shown in the diagram of [37]). The systems tested included Dardel, an HPE Cray EX supercomputer with AMD EPYC Zen2 processors and a 12 PB Lustre file system, running GCC 11.2.0 and Cray-MPICH; Vega, a EuroHPC petascale system featuring AMD EPYC 7H12 CPUs, Nvidia A100 GPUs, and Mellanox HDR100 InfiniBand, running GCC 12.3.0 and OpenMPI 4.1.2.1; and MareNostrum 5 (MN5), a EuroHPC pre-exascale system equipped with Intel Sapphire Rapids CPUs, Nvidia Hopper H100 GPUs, and ConnectX-7 NDR200 InfiniBand, operating with GCC 12.3.0 and OpenMPI 4.1.5.

Figure 1: Hybrid BIT1 total simulation and optimized mover function using 16 and 64 ranks per node on Vega for 20000 times steps.

3.1.1 Hybrid MPI and OpenMP/OpenACC BIT1

An in-depth investigation into BIT1’s performance was conducted, focusing on both intra-node and inter-node testing to evaluate the impact of hybrid MPI and OpenMP/OpenACC approaches on execution time. The results, shown in Fig. 1, demonstrate that using MPI in combination with OpenMP or OpenACC significantly improves performance. With 16 MPI ranks, the hybrid MPI+OpenMP version reduced total simulation

Figure 2: BIT1 optimized mover function - scaling up to 100 Nodes (12,800 MPI ranks) on *Dardel* for 200000 times steps.

time by 53.4% (from 845.69 to 394.33 seconds) and mover function time by 69.3% (from 302.02 to 92.69 seconds). The MPI+OpenACC version further improved performance, reducing total simulation time by 57.0% to 355.85 seconds and mover function time by 70.3% to 89.61 seconds. Scaling to 64 MPI ranks, total simulation time dropped to 164.13 seconds and mover function time to 66.91 seconds, while adding OpenMP threads further reduced total simulation time to 42.07 seconds (a 74.4% reduction) and mover function time to 66.91 seconds (a 37.2% reduction). The best performance was achieved with the hybrid MPI+OpenACC version at 64 ranks, reducing both times to 32.32 seconds, representing an 80.3% reduction in total simulation time and a 51.7% reduction in mover function time compared to the baseline. Results from *NJ* and *Vega* show that BIT1 benefits from multicore CPUs through better core utilization via parallelization.

Investigation into the scalability of hybrid BIT1 on CPUs, as shown in Fig.1, reveals a significant performance improvement as the number of MPI ranks increases from 2 (as reported in [37], D1.5 and D5.1) to 64, with noticeable improvements in both the total simulation and optimized mover function execution times, indicating that hybrid BIT1 scales effectively. To validate these findings, a second system, *Dardel*, was used for further investigation, specifically focusing on the optimized mover function with OpenMP (since OpenACC was not utilized). When scaling up to 100 nodes and 200,000 time steps on *Dardel*, our analysis demonstrates substantial performance gains with the hybrid MPI+OpenMP versions of BIT1 for both the mover function and total simulation. For the BIT1 mover function, as shown in Fig. 2, the MPI version with 1 node takes 260.85 seconds, while the hybrid MPI+OpenMP version improves this to 149.47 seconds, achieving a 42.7% speedup. Scaling to 10 nodes, the mover function time decreases to

Figure 3: BIT1 Total Simulation - scaling up to 100 Nodes (12,800 MPI ranks) on *Dardel* for 200000 times steps.

11.18 seconds for MPI and 10.81 seconds for MPI+OpenMP, resulting in a 3.3% improvement. At higher node counts (50 and 100 nodes), the performance stabilizes, with times of 7.45 seconds and 8.26 seconds for MPI, and 7.31 seconds and 8.23 seconds for MPI+OpenMP, respectively.

Similarly, for the BIT1 total simulation, as shown in Fig. 3, with 1 node, the MPI version completes in 698.48 seconds, while the hybrid MPI+OpenMP version takes 696.85 seconds, resulting in only a negligible improvement. At 2 nodes, the MPI time of 247.55 seconds reduces to 244.02 seconds with MPI+OpenMP, yielding a 1.0% speedup. The most significant improvements occur at 5 nodes, where the total simulation time drops from 148.03 seconds to 132.85 seconds, achieving a 10.2% speedup. At 20 nodes, the MPI version takes 68.58 seconds, while the hybrid version further reduces this to 61.83 seconds, resulting in an 11.9% speedup. However, at 50 nodes, the total simulation time increases for MPI to 106.63 seconds, while it decreases to 87.66 seconds for MPI+OpenMP, demonstrating a 17.8% improvement. Finally, at 100 nodes, the total simulation times are 150.67 seconds for MPI and 94.22 seconds for MPI+OpenMP, resulting in a 37.5% speedup. This analysis highlights the advantages of hybrid parallelization in optimizing both the mover function and total simulation performance on *Dardel*.

3.1.2 Accelerating BIT1 Asynchronously on Vega and MN5

The performance of the accelerated BIT1 code on two EuroHPC supercomputers, *Vega A100* and *MN5 H100* NVIDIA GPU/ACC partitions, was critically analyzed, discussed, and compared, scaling up to 16 nodes with 200 timesteps. This served as an initial step in preparing for the upcoming EuroHPC exascale supercomputer. Similar to previous tests (as reported in [37], D1.5 and D5.1), each configuration utilized 4 MPI ranks, with the GPU versions having dedicated GPUs on both systems.

For the total simulation on Vega and in Fig. 4, the slowest GPU version (4 MPI + 4 GPUs OpenMP UM / OMP Target Tasks Nowait) took 273.18 seconds on 1 node, while the fastest GPU version (4 MPI + 4 GPUs OpenACC UM / ACC Parallel Async(n)) reduced this to 261.34 seconds, resulting in a 4.34% improvement.

Figure 4: BIT1 Total Simulation execution time(s) for 200 time steps up to 16 Nodes using OpenMP and OpenACC Unified Memory on *Vega A100* and *MN5 H100* NVIDIA GPUs.

Figure 5: BIT1 Optimized mover function execution time(s) for 200 time steps up to 16 Nodes using OpenMP and OpenACC Unified Memory on *Vega A100* and *MN5 H100* NVIDIA GPUs.

At 16 nodes, Async(n) reduced the execution time to 22.33 seconds, improving by 1.97% over the slowest GPU version (22.79 seconds). However, the CPU version on Vega remained faster, taking 42.46 seconds on 1 node and 3.29 seconds on 16 nodes. On MN5, the GPU versions outperformed those on Vega, with the slowest GPU version (4 MPI + 4 GPUs OpenMP UM / OMP Target Tasks Nowait) taking 162.94 seconds on 1 node, while the fastest GPU version (4 MPI + 4 GPUs OpenACC UM / ACC Parallel Async(n)) improved to 153.00 seconds, a 6.10% improvement. On 16 nodes, Async(n) completed the simulation in 14.99 seconds, a 2.60% improvement over the slowest GPU version (15.39 seconds). MN5's CPU version outperformed Vega's, with times of 21.17 seconds on 1 node and 2.42 seconds on 16 nodes.

For the mover function (Fig. 5), Vega's Async(n) achieved a 4.89% improvement on 1 node (from 69.31 to 65.92 seconds) and a 2.95% improvement on 16 nodes (from 5.08 to 4.93 seconds). The CPU version, however, completed the mover function much faster, taking only 5.49 seconds on 1 node and 0.13 seconds on 16 nodes. On MN5, Async(n)

showed a 17.22% improvement on 1 node (from 56.86 to 47.08 seconds) and completed the mover in 3.31 seconds on 16 nodes, a 3.50% improvement over the slowest GPU version (3.43 seconds). MN5’s CPU version also outperformed Vega’s, completing the mover in 4.62 seconds on 1 node and 0.12 seconds on 16 nodes.

Using NVIDIA Nsight Systems v2022 (Vega) and v2024 (MN5), crucial insights into the porting efforts and acceleration of the particle mover function on GPUs are revealed. As previously shown in [37], the primary kernel consumed 99.7% of the GPU execution time without overlapping computation and communication. Now, both *Vega* and *MN5* display overlapping kernels, with data transfers and computations managed together for accurate results without blocking the CPU, thereby improving execution time in the mover function.

Figure 6: NVIDIA Nsight Systems v2022 OpenACC UM / ACC Parallel Async(n) View - GPU porting of BIT1 mover function on *Vega* with 1 time step.

As seen in Fig. 6 and 7, the primary kernel consumption has been reduced due to overlapping computation and communication from 99.7% on *NJ* (shown in [37]) to 59.8% on *Vega* and 60.6% on *MN5*, respectively.

While the GPU-accelerated versions of BIT1, particularly the 4 MPI + 4 GPUs OpenACC UM / ACC Parallel Async(n) configuration, demonstrate strong scalability and significant performance improvements, the CPU version remains the fastest. Future work will prioritize further optimizing GPU performance to close this gap, especially for large-scale plasma simulations that demand high throughput and efficient GPU utilization across multiple nodes. However, despite these promising results, a critical challenge arises: data transfer constraints during each PIC cycle. Profiling results illustrated in Fig. 6 and 7 highlight the adverse effects of copying substantial data from the CPU to the GPU at each time step, resulting in notable performance bottlenecks. To address this issue, it is essential to minimize large data transfers between the CPU and GPU during each iteration. Exploring CUDA streams and particle batch processing with OpenMP Target across multiple GPUs per node presents a promising approach to streamline both data transfer and processing, as also noted in [7]. Additionally, an investigation will be conducted using openPMD with Hybrid BIT1 and GPU offloading to further eliminate I/O bottlenecks previously discovered in [39], resolved in [38], and reviewed in [36].

Figure 7: NVIDIA Nsight Systems v2024 OpenACC UM / ACC Parallel Async(n) View - GPU porting of BIT1 mover function on *MN5* with 1 time step.

3.2 GENE/GENE-X

3.2.1 GENE

The GENE code, which will compute the transport in the core of ITER in our Grand Challenge is fully ported with respect to the physics needed for the target runs. GENE employs the mid-layer GTENSOR which abstracts the vendor specific implementations from the application code. There are three backends implemented, one for NVIDIA, AMD and INTEL GPUs. The GPU code is already regularly used in production runs, but is still under optimization and development, especially regarding the AMD GPUs. Performance is best on NVIDIA GPUs but inferior on MI250X (the AMD GPUs used on LUMI). The optimization there is work in progress.

3.2.2 GENE-X

The time integration in GENE-X code, which simulates plasma turbulence in the edge region and scrape of layer (SOL) of magnetic fusion confinement (MFC) devices, is now fully ported for GPU offloading. For compute kernels that are native to GENE-X, we support directive-based programming models such as OpenACC and OpenMP offload, commonly abbreviated below as ACC and OMPX respectively. Our field solvers are powered by an in-house multigrid GMRES (MGMRES) solver called PARALLAX. The porting effort of PARALLAX is done separately from GENE-X using low-level programming such as CUDA and HIP on its C++ layer called PAccX. The runs done in this section were performed on MareNostrum 5 (MN5) ACC partition with specifications mentioned above.

Table 1: Problem size and resource allocations for GENE-X overview with TCV-X21 equilibrium.

Dimension	Num. points	MPI procs	Num. points per procs
RZ	212387	1	212387
φ	16	4	4
v_{\parallel}	40	1	40
μ	20	10	2
species	2	2	1
Number of MPI processes			80
Number of nodes			20
Number of OpenMP threads			1600
Number of GPUs			80

Overview of the performance improvements. Here we provide an overview of the performance improvements of our GPU offloading efforts in GENE-X. The problem size, problem settings and MPI decomposition are provided in Table. 1. Here we use 20 nodes, 80 MPI processes and 80 GPUs in total. F90, OMP, ACC, OMPX labels are respectively referring to runtime mode with full Fortran on CPUs with OpenMP, Fortran/C++ hybrid on CPUs with OpenMP, OpenACC and OpenMP offload on GPUs. The suffix + indicates that CUDA field solvers from PARALLAX and PAccX are used.

Figure 8: Average elapsed time of the time integration in GENE-X (left) and the composition of each profiling regions in percentage (right). The colormaps in the right figure are isolated in each columns.

The average elapsed time per MPI process of the time integration part of GENE-X is shown in the left side of Fig. 8. The color variation shows different parts in GENE-X time-stepping scheme. Op is an abbreviation of operator and three operators in the figure are the major stencil operators native to GENE-X. The figure compares bar plots of each runtime modes and it displays significant performance improvement compared to full Fortran run even by simply porting the compute kernels to C++. Using OpenACC and OpenMP offload on GPUs further strikes significant improvements on GENE-X native operators. Even with CUDA on GPUs, the field solvers still pose to be the bottlenecks and this is further shown by the right side of Fig. 8.

Figure 9: The total speedups of GENE-X time integration w.r.t. full Fortran run (right y axis) and Fortran/C++ hybrid run (left y axis) on CPUs.

Since we interoperate the code between Fortran and C++, there are two contexts of speedups: 1) compared to the original Fortran kernels, 2) compared to the kernels on the new auxiliary C++ layer. Both speedups can be seen in Fig. 9 where the right y axis displays the former and the left one displays the later. Compared to Fortran, the performance has improved 14.8 times via OpenACC together with CUDA field solvers and 3.1 times compared to host OpenMP on C++. The improvements by OpenMP offload are slightly lower compared to the ones by OpenACC. This is commonly observed in application built by NVIDIA compilers and run on NVIDIA GPUs.

The speedups can further be broken down to each profiling regions which are shown in Fig. 10. The left and the right figure display the speedups compared to Fortran and C++ respectively. `Ohm's law solver`, `Quasineutrality eq solver`, `Ampere's law solver` are the field solvers. `Op copy`, `Op axpy` and `Op linear combination` are simple arithmetic operators which are included here reference under the assumption that the Fortran kernels have near the peak performance. The GENE-X native operators showcase remarkable performance improvement with both OpenACC and OpenMP offload. However, the CUDA-powered field solvers shown in ACC+ and OMPX+ have less significant speedup.

Figure 10: Speedups of each major profiling regions compared to the Fortran runtime (left) and the C++ runtime (right) on CPUs. The colormaps in the right figure are isolated in each rows.

Scaling behaviour on the RZ dimension. The contrast difference between MCF reactors and experimental devices are in their poloidal size and the magnetic field strength. These two factors determine the numerical resolution on the poloidal cross section. In GENE-X, this translates to the number of points on RZ dimensions. Thus, scaling experiments on the RZ dimension is necessary for us to investigate the performance reliability of GENE-X in our target ITER case. Here we start the experiment from the same poloidal resolution as Table. 1 which has 212,387 RZ points the scaling up to a case with 2,621,778 RZ points which is around 12.3 times larger from where we start. In this experiment, we use the same number of nodes, GPUs, MPI processes as the previous case in Table. 1. The specifications of the other dimensions also stay constant and prescribed in Table. 2

The largest case here is estimated to use 45 GB of CUDA memory per GPU which is already 70.3% of the maximum capacity in MN5 ACC partition. This estimate only includes allocation on GENE-X side and does not consider allocation from inside the CUDA-powered multigrid GMRES solvers. The target ITER case is estimated to be around 20 times larger than this which means that we will run into GPU memory limit issue in the future.

Table 2: Constant parameters for the scaling experiments on the RZ dimension with 20 nodes.

Dimension	Num. points	MPI procs	Num. points per procs
φ	16	4	4
v_{\parallel}	10	1	10
μ	20	10	2
species	2	2	1

The scaling of the average elapsed time of both full Fortran run on CPU and OpenACC with CUDA-powered field solvers are shown in Fig. 11 by stacked area plot analogous

to the bar plots in Fig. 8. The stack of field solvers in red includes preprocessing time on GENE-X, i.e. matrix updates, while the dotted red stack shows the iterative solving time by the multigrid GMRES library PARALLAX and PAccX.

The top figure of Fig. 11 shows near linear scaling behaviour of all profiling region in GENE-X. The preprocessing time of the field solvers is only a small fraction compared to the actual solving time. Similar to the result in the overview, `Op Vlasov static` is the bottleneck in the Fortran layer. This stencil operator is the largest and the most arithmetically complex in GENE-X.

The bottom figure of Fig. 11 show super linear scaling behaviour of the total elapsed time. We can also see that the main contributor to such scaling behaviour is the field solvers. The performance of the CUDA-powered field solvers seems to be deteriorating as the problem size becomes larger in the RZ dimension. The multigrid GMRES solver only solves one poloidal plane at a time. This means that the kernel occupancy is solely determined by the number of RZ points. Despite of higher occupancy which commonly leads to better throughput, the CUDA kernel in the field solvers suffers in performance. This requires further investigation of the CUDA kernel in field solver with better profiler such as Nsight compute.

Figure 11: Average elapsed time of the time integration in GENE-X with respect of up-scaling the number of points in the RZ dimension. Full Fortran (top), combination of OpenACC and CUDA field solvers (bottom) are used.

Figure 12: Weak scaling of PICongPU on GH200 nodes taken from [11] for the JUPITER benchmark suite compared to other codes.

Conclusion. The native compute kernels in GENE-X show remarkable performance improvements via OpenACC and OpenMP offload on GPUs. The results above are performed with CUDA-aware MPI in MN5. Optionally, we support NCCL for collective communication, i.e. allreduce, mainly for machine that is difficult to leverage CUDA-aware MPI due to mixed-language mixed-vendor complication that we have in GENE-X. This complication occurs in Raven supercomputer in Max-Planck Computing and Data Facility. While we now fully support GENE-X time integration on GPU by combining directive-based approach, i.e. OpenACC and OpenMP offload, with CUDA and HIP for the field solvers, more performance improvements are still left to be desired in the field solvers.

3.3 PICongPU

PICongPU [40] profits from cross-platform accelerator support using *alpaka* [41, 21, 20] for portable heterogeneous programming. *alpaka* uses a parallelisation hierarchy similar to that of CUDA and HIP, including grids, blocks, warps, threads and elements as levels in the parallel hierarchy, defining shared or non-shared memory access and parallelism for each level, see Fig. 14.

As the levels are abstract they can be mapped to the actual parallelism hierarchy of a specific compute architecture depending on which programming model is selected as an *alpaka* backend [14]. In the course of the project *SYCL* was added to the backends, complementing backends such as CUDA, HIP/ROCm or OpenMP. In order to allow for extensive testing a complex CI/CD workflow to test backends for a variety of hardware platforms and compilers was set up as well as first kernels for continuous performance tests were developed.

In addition to work on *alpaka* we also refactored and accelerated our parallel memory allocator / manager *mallocMC* built with *alpaka* to speed up small object allocation and manage device memory. For more details see section 5.

Figure 13: Strong scaling of PICongPU on LUMI-G for the figure of merit as detailed in the PlasmaPEPSC project description. Green triangles indicate use of GPU-aware MPI while blue dots stand for standard MPI.

We furthermore developed the *LLAMA* library for easy selection of memory layout for complex data types when switching compute architectures, see section 5.

Using *alpaka*, PICongPU is able to run the same simulation code on a large variety of devices, making adaption to specific EuroHPC systems a matter of recompilation. As an example, *alpaka* was used early in tests of GPU programming models for LUMI [20], showing superior performance compared to *Kokkos* and *SYCL* and on-par performance compared to native implementations.

As a consequence, PICongPU could present close to perfect weak scaling on both LUMI. Fig. 13 shows the strong scaling for PICongPU’s figure of merit on LUMI-G, indicating that PICongPU is on a good path towards reaching its goals.

It was also selected for the JUPITER benchmark suite designed to estimate the performance of simulation codes for the upcoming EuroHPC exascale computer JUPITER as part of the JUPITER early access program JUREAP. Fig. 12 shows the weak scaling performance measured on JUWELS BOOSTER as part of the JUPITER early access program to estimate performance for the EuroHPC JUPITER system [11].

3.4 Vlasiator

Deliverable D5.1 described the approach taken in porting Vlasiator to GPU architectures, consisting of memory management, Vlasov solver porting, and field solver porting. The year of 2024 resulted in significant advancements in the operation of the Vlasov solver on GPU architectures.

Memory management of the Vlasov solver and internal Vlasiator data structures was improved to the point where sample profiles were able to run several time steps without page faults of any data between the host and device. A significant performance bottleneck

was identified in use of many small kernel launches, resulting in device slowdowns. A major constituent of memory management, the block management of Vlasiator’s sparse velocity space, was completely re-designed to operate wholly on-device using parallel batch operations over the whole simulation domain. The majority of these improvements are detailed in a publication, submitted to the proceedings of the ASTRONUM-2024 conference, and available as a preprint [5]. The performance obtained in the code version described in this preprint is able to, for an artificial test case, exceed the performance of the CPU code path when comparing 1/4 CPU node against 1/4 CUDA GPU node on a HPC cluster. A detailed development plan exists for extending this performance to more generic use cases and improving performance overall.

The porting of the field solver to GPU operations has proceeded as planned. Assembly-level evaluation of loop operations accessing our field solver data motivated a more comprehensive overhaul of our field solver library FSgrid. A result is that FSgrid will be updated to provide a portable looping interface, resulting in portable code, which should provide optimized memory access patterns for both GPU and CPU use cases, without requiring a thorough re-write of the physics code describing the field solver equations. This is of especial importance when considering physical domain boundaries found in Vlasiator, such as the stepwise spherical inner boundary, requiring special management for different layers of the boundary domain.

One major issue is an apparent performance gap between the CUDA and HIP versions of the code, running on NVIDIA and AMD hardware respectively. Implementing merged large overall kernels and pruning page faults have not yet succeeded in bridging this performance gap. This suggests that detailed analysis of AMD performance counters together is required in order to find the root cause. Current analysis indicates memory access patterns and cache utilization may play a role in this.

4 GPU Acceleration Strategies

GPU accelerators, often called *devices* need a *host*, typically a CPU, to receive data for computation and initiate processes on the GPU. The process of copying data from host to device and back takes time and is limited by the latency and bandwidth between CPU and GPU. Such data transfer can be either evoked by the user or managed by a common memory interface which mirrors memory pages from the CPU to the GPU and vice versa. Copying data and starting processes from the host on the device is called *offloading*. Execution of processes on the device can be performed in parallel to processes on the CPU.

At best, the waiting time for a full offloading cycle, meaning copying memory from host to device, executing code on the device and copying data back from device to host is at best spent doing computation in parallel on the CPU, e.g. for inter-node communication.

In any case, the speed up of time to solution achieved by executing code on the accelerator should outperform execution on the CPU including the time needed for offloading.

In the following we will discuss the many dimensions of using accelerator devices in PlasmaPEPSC and present lessons learned so far.

4.1 Programming Interfaces

Figure 14: Mapping of the alpaka parallel hierarchies Grid, Block, Warp, Thread and Element (right) to a multi-core CPU (left) and GPU (center).

The two main vendors currently dominating the market for GPU accelerators are Nvidia, and to a smaller part, AMD. For two decades Nvidia has been providing the proprietary *CUDA* programming interface. AMD later introduced the *HIP/ROCm* interface that was heavily inspired by CUDA. In fact, AMD provides a HIP/CUDA translator, enabling the execution of many CUDA codes on AMD hardware without big changes.

Non-vendor-specific programming models include *OpenCL* [9], which today is no longer competitive and has been surpassed by *SYCL*, directive-based models such as *OpenMP* [28] and *OpenACC* [27] or high-level APIs such as Intel’s *OneAPI/SYCL* [13]. While for many years only vendor compilers and tool chains were available to compile accelerator code, with the advent of [19] almost all major compilers, including Open Source compilers, understand accelerator code.

Still, cross-platform code that can be executed efficiently on a variety of GPU platforms is sparse, as vendor-specific interfaces change rapidly and vendors invest in these rather than cross-platform solutions.

Thus, cross-platform code usually adapts open standards (OpenMP, OpenACC, OpenCL). Maintaining these standards and providing hardware specific implementations requires significant resources and long-term support is not guaranteed. Thus, another approach is to develop light-weight programming interfaces that abstract across existing programming standards, providing a stable interface for portable parallel programming. Examples include Sandia’s Kokkos [35] and LLNL’s Raja [18] efforts. In PlasmaPEPSC the Helmholtz solution *alpaka* is used by PIconGPU, providing close-to-native performance for GPUs, CPUs and FPGAs. It provides mapping of a parallel hierarchy similar to CUDA including Grid, Block, Warp, Thread and Element to different accelerator back ends, see Fig. 14.

4.1.1 Multi-GPU Communication Interfaces

On the lowest level, APIs such as CUDA provide multi-device pipelining in a single node. GPU-aware MPI [2, 25] now offers inter-node communication across nodes, multiple MPI

Figure 15: Architecture of a quad-GPU node of AMD MI250X, as featured in the LUMI supercomputer.

processes sharing a single GPU and pipelining of MPI processes. Communication libraries like *nccl* [26] or *rccl* [3] complement MPI for multi-GPU, multi-node communication. Another library of interest is *libfabric* [1] which operates as a back end to e.g. MPI but also models for partitioned global address space approaches, which are not covered here.

We provide an extensive characterization of the Infinity Fabric Interconnect [33]. This high-performance interconnect is present on multi-GPU AMD systems, and in particular is the intra-node interconnect used in the EuroHPC’s LUMI supercomputer, connecting together the four AMD MI250X GPUs on each node. Fig. 15 describes the complex mesh drawn by the Infinity Fabric Interconnect in such system. The first contributor to this complexity is the unique design of MI250X GPUs, which are composed, on a single board, of two independent Graphics Compute Dies (GCDs). A GCD is seen from the user perspective as a single GPU, with its own memory, and own compute units. In addition, the Infinity Fabric interconnect exposes four tiers of bandwidth, depending on the observed link. First, CPU-GPU Infinity Fabric links have a 36 GB/s bandwidth in each direction; in addition, GCD-GCD Infinity Fabric links have three tiers of bandwidth, respectively 200 GB/s per direction between same-GPU GCDs, 100 GB/s per direction for the pairs GCD2-GCD4 and GCD0-GCD6, and 50 GB/s per direction for all other pairs of connected GCDs. Furthermore, in this configuration, several hops might be required for data to transit within some pairs of GCDs, for example, between GCD5 and GCD6, one additional hop through GCD7 or GCD4 would be required. Those characteristics create a high-complexity mesh, which user might find trouble some to leverage directly.

Thankfully, high-level interfaces, such as RCCL and GPU-aware MPI, abstract this complexity within a user-friendly set of API. From there, the question of performance and ability of those interfaces to leverage the full link bandwidth is raised. To answer this question, we evaluate the performance and crucial user-guided aspects of using those high-level interfaces to leverage this interconnect. We further evaluate lower-level interfaces, such as explicit data movements with HIP, and GPU-side direct access to remote CPU memory.

Explicit Movements. We first evaluate the CPU-GPU data movements, where we copy data from CPU memory to GPU memory using the dedicated `hipMemcpy` API.

For this experiment, we evaluated two variants, both from pageable memory, simply allocated on the CPU-side with `malloc`, and pinned memory, allocated with `hipHostMalloc`. Our results show that movements from pageable memory achieved 71% of the theoretical bandwidth, while pinned memory achieves 79% of the theoretical bandwidth. This indicates quantitatively how memory pinning is essential to achieve the highest performance for data movements. For GPU-GPU peer-to-peer data movements, our experiments demonstrate the inability of the default configuration to leverage the full Infinity Fabric link bandwidth. Indeed, by default, explicit peer-to-peer data movements using `hipMemcpyPeer` rely on System Direct Memory Access (SDMA) Engines. This hardware feature is responsible for moving data in a way that copy can be overlap with GPU kernel execution. When using those SDMA engines, we observe a low utilization of the Infinity Fabric link, as low as 25% for data movements between two GCDs located on the same physical GPU. The use of SDMA engines can be disabled by setting the environment variable `HSA_ENABLE_SDMA=0`; however, setting this options removes the ability to overlap kernel execution with data movements. Therefore, a naturally-appearing alternative, which does not rely on SDMA engines, neither blocking on explicit data movements, is to use direct access from GPU kernel code.

Direct access. We evaluate the performance of GPU-side kernel-level access to remote, CPU-located data. In this configuration, often referred to as *Unified Memory*, a single pointer is used to designate memory, which is located either on CPU or GPU memory. In our experiment, we allocate managed memory, using the `hipMallocManaged` API, and ensure an initial placement on CPU memory. We then use a GPU kernel, reading from this allocation. For this first experiment, we show that direct access over Infinity Fabric to CPU-located data achieves up to 70% of the theoretical Infinity Fabric link bandwidth, which is comparable to the level of performance obtained with explicit data movements. This shows that direct access from GPU kernel code to remote memory is a viable option for developers to use in their application in terms of performance, while removing the need for finely-tuned explicit data movements. We complete our analysis of GPU kernel-level access to CPU memory with an evaluation of the XNACK feature present in MI250X GPUs. This feature, used in combination with managed memory, migrates data to the GPU when accessed from kernel code, instead of performing a read over the Infinity Fabric Interconnect. This is aimed at improving data locality. Our experiments show that this approach exhibited as low as 8% of the theoretical CPU-GPU Infinity Fabric link bandwidth. This is expected, as the overhead of migrating data on the first access can only be counterbalanced by repeated future access to this same data. As our benchmarking does not contain any data reuse, this benefit is not observed. However, XNACK feature can be potentially provide performance improvement when using unified memory in GPU-accelerated applications. In terms of peer-to-peer GPU-GPU data movements, this options allowed reaching higher bandwidth than when using explicit data movements, generally on the level of 50% of the theoretical Infinity Fabric bandwidth.

High-level Interfaces, RCCL and MPI. We evaluate GPU collective communications, where several GPUs execute collective operations. For this purpose, we compare the RCCL library, which is specialized for AMD GPUs, with GPU-aware MPI, which provides a generic API for all types of accelerators, and CPU-only systems. We use three types of collectives, one-to-all, where one GPU sends data to all others, all-to-one,

where all GPUs send data to a single one, and all-to-all, where all GPUs both send and receive data. Our results show that RCCL consistently outperforms GPU-aware MPI, with regards to latency for collective operations on 1 MB data size. We suggest that the multi-process approach used in MPI causes high overhead of inter-process communication, compared to the RCCL approach. Further study is however required for inter-node GPU collectives, as the behavior of the RCCL library and GPU-aware MPI might differ when compared to intra-node. PIconGPU makes use of NCCL, RCCL, GPU-aware MPI and libfabric either for inter-process communication or in-memory coupling of codes (see D4.2) on systems where these libraries are available.

4.2 Performance Optimisation Strategies

Figure 16: Comparing the strategy to accelerate critical paths in a code (left) vs. using an abstraction layer to separate code implementation from accelerated code (right).

Strategies for accelerating existing CPU code conventionally used critical path analysis to identify those parts in a code that dominated the overall execution time and could profit from the parallelization on the accelerator, see Fig. 16, left. However, while in theory this strategy sounds sensible, in reality one observes that instead optimizing the data flow of the application is key to achieve optimization. This means that offloading usually requires changing data formats and data flow paradigms of the code, resulting in major code changes all over the source code. Porting efforts then usually develop into porting more and more parts of the code to the accelerator, to minimize data movement. We have observed this when porting BIT to GPUs where time consuming parts of the code were ported one by one.

A more time consuming strategy that usually results in better performance is to refactor the application code into user-facing code that provides a convenient interface to access all data and encapsulates all performance critical code via an API, see Fig. 16, right. This design is chosen, albeit in two distinct ways, by Vlasiator and PIconGPU.

Another strategy for porting is to use high level libraries that provide optimizations for accelerators out of the box. This approach is heavily used by GENE/GENE-X. It has the advantage that the optimization is done by the library maintainers. Furthermore,

code can use the high level library instructions that typically abstract the underlying programming model and can provide portability across various platforms. A disadvantage is the strong dependency on these libraries, which must provide the performance needed by the application and be maintained for a long time.

4.2.1 GPU Matrix Processing Units

Matrix processing units have been inspired by the rise of machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) as yet another way of accelerating matrix-based operations. With growing interest in ML/AI the capabilities of these units have grown and added significantly to the overall compute power of GPUs. They are best for repetitive matrix operations or, more general, tensor operations, which are frequent in AI/ML. Similarly, some codes such as GENE/GENE-X use a lot of linear algebra operations from existing libraries, fast Fourier transforms and other matrix operations that benefit from vendor-specific acceleration through matrix processing units.

Nvidia’s implementation of GPU matrix processing units, named Tensor Cores, have been widely studied in the literature. However, the study of AMD’s implementation of those matrix processing units, namely Matrix Cores, is still sparse in the literature. However, as EuroHPC’s LUMI supercomputer features such hardware unit, as part of the AMD MI250X GPU, evaluation of Matrix Cores is a crucial element for efficient codes. Therefore, we provide a first study of AMD Matrix Core [32], where we discuss the opportunities of programming those hardware units, from the lowest level of compiler-level intrinsics, up to highest level of linear algebra libraries, such as GPU-accelerated BLAS. We associate this study of programming interfaces by a systematic performance evaluation, along with measurement of power efficiency.

Low-level benchmarking. We first performed an evaluation of the low-level rocWMMA library, which directly maps C-level API calls to Matrix Cores instructions, with minimal to no overhead. This library only allows simple matrix operations, which are directly mappable to Matrix Cores abilities, therefore, the shape and datatypes of the matrices are strictly constrained. For this evaluation, we developed a micro-benchmarking approach, where we execute repeated Matrix Core instructions on all the available hardware units, for a significant amount of time.

High-level programmability. The study of the highest-level rocBLAS library highlighted some important considerations with regards to mixed-precision GEMM operations. Using the single- and double-precision GEMM routines in rocBLAS, we were able to achieve a high percentage of floating-point throughput, relative to expected performance in the hypothesis of computations fully executed on Matrix Cores. Fig. 17 presents the results for various matrix sizes. We observe that the rocBLAS library achieves 90% and 100% of the throughput measured in our ideal microbenchmark setup, for DGEMM and SGEMM, respectively. This indicates that rocBLAS provides close-to-ideal utilization of Matrix Cores for single- and double-precision GEMM operations, without any low-level programming efforts. We demonstrate in our study that the performance gap between double- and single-precision Matrix Core operations is induced by a high power consumption observed in double-precision, causing performance degradation to preserve hardware integrity. Therefore, it is advisable, both from the efficiency and raw performance perspectives, that single-precision is used when applicable, instead of double-precision. This

is despite identical theoretical throughput for both datatypes.

Figure 17: Floating-point arithmetic throughput on a single MI250X GCD for rocBLAS single- and double-precision GEMM operation.

Mixed-precision GEMM. In rocBLAS, single and double precision GEMM operations are exposed through the unambiguous SGEMM and DGEMM routines in rocBLAS, where all operands are of single- or double- precision, respectively. However, when considering mixed-precision GEMM operation, three variants are available to the user, based on the datatype of the various operands. Table 3 lists those three variants, for a GEMM operation $D \leftarrow \alpha AB + \beta C$, where A , B , C and D are arbitrary-size matrices, and α and β are scalars. Fig. 18 presents the achieved floating-point throughput for those three mixed-precision GEMM routines. We observe that HGEMM exhibit very low floating-point throughput of 20 TFLOPS, compared to the two other HHS and HSS routines, and compared to the theoretical 191.5 TFLOPS provided by mixed-precision Matrix Cores. In further profiling, we identified that the HGEMM routine was not able to leverage any Matrix Core instructions, and executes instead all computations on regular SIMD units, which exhibit significantly lower theoretical performance than Matrix Cores. At the hardware-level, mixed-precision Matrix Cores only support the $D \leftarrow AB + C$ operation with A/B in half-precision, and C/D in single-precision. Therefore, intuitively, only the HSS operation should be able to fully leverage Matrix Cores performance. However, as presented on Fig. 18, it appears that the HHS operation outperforms the HSS operation. We suggest that this is because of the α/β scaling, which cannot be performed on Matrix Cores, and must be performed on regular SIMD units, where floating-point throughput is lower. This is an aspect that we demonstrate in further profiling of our benchmark code.

Operation	typeAB	typeCD	Compute type (α , β)
HGEMM	FP16	FP16	FP16
HHS	FP16	FP16	FP32
HSS	FP16	FP32	FP32

Table 3: Operand datatypes in a mixed-precision GEMM operation $D \leftarrow \alpha AB + \beta C$ (A , B , C , D matrices, α , β scalars), exposed as part of the rocBLAS library.

Figure 18: Floating-point arithmetic throughput on a single MI250X GCD for the three mixed-precision GEMM routines exposed in rocBLAS, see Table 3 for details on those operations.

One interesting feature of matrix processing units is that they can operate for a specific floating point or even integer type, thus often codes can profit from these units when the arithmetic precision can be reduced.

Extensive tests by the PIconGPU team to use matrix processing units on PIconGPU did not see an advantage of using them as the code was already highly optimized and using tensor cores did not provide sufficient increase in speed up. This may change for special physics cases such as calculating rate equations in situ further down the line.

4.2.2 Mixed Precision on GPUs

Reducing numerical precision whenever possible is a rewarding approach as it leads to performance increase in three central aspects important for heterogeneous computing. As there is no reward without work, it is essential in complex codes to understand how the use of mixed precision calculations throughout the code influences the long term numerical stability, accuracy of output parameters of interest and accuracy of quantities derived from simulation parameters.

Another dimension to consider is the precision of input parameters to simulations, as these are very often related to experimental measurements. It is clear that many of these measurements are not so high in precision that they warrant a high precision numerical input. However, due to nonlinearities, the resulting output may be sensitive to the input precision. This, however, now means uncertainty quantification and thus ensemble runs to understand the sensitivity due to the change in precision. We thus mainly focus on where one can reduce precision of data representations in the codes that do not change the output accuracy significantly.

One way to change data representations (and thus precision) without changing all of the code is using the *LLAMA* [10] library developed by HZDR, see the description below. Other ways involve e.g. using C++ templates or simply defining data types with certain precision.

The benefits of using reduced precision are fourfold. First of all and obviously, memory use is reduced. This means the systems simulated either take less memory or one can extend the system size, thus requiring less resources or making better use of existing resources. Second, when accessing shared memory resources, more processes (or

threads in GPU language) can now run in parallel as each process has a smaller memory footprint and thus more processes can access the shared memory simultaneously. Third, throughput per data object is increased, as for the same bandwidth more objects can be moved or copied. For example, reducing the memory footprint per particle position by half by using cell-relative positions instead of coordinate center positions as done in PIconGPU, one can in principle stream twice as much position objects as before using the same bandwidth. Fourth, the overall output volume of data is greatly reduced, which is profitable both for communication, e.g. via MPI, but also for later storage on disk.

From these benefits it becomes obvious why using mixed or reduced precision is worthwhile even when it means extensively studying its effects on simulation output.

5 Heterogeneous Memory Approaches

In most of the current heterogeneous compute environments one is confronted with a complex memory hierarchy that should be utilized wisely in order to maximize throughput. The overall goal, as nicely seen in roof line models for code performance [17], many plasma simulations are memory bound, so the majority of time spend is in moving/copying data rather than doing computations, thus not reaching the maximum number of FLOPs/s theoretically provided by the compute hardware. Typically, one thus focuses on repeated use of data in memory, or more general, on data locality. The less data has to be moved or copied, the better.

Many design parameters determine the memory hierarchy. These are latency of memory operations, available bandwidth for moving or copying data, conflicts in writing data concurrently (conflicts in reading data concurrently are scarce due to modern accelerators providing efficient concurrent memory reads) and parallel data access. In essence, all of these parameters and the code implementation lead to an effective throughput for data across memory hierarchies. As such, figures of merit often are formulated in terms of these throughput. As an example, for PIconGPU a weighed average of particle and cell data objects processed per second is used to understand the performance of the code rather than the time to solution for a specific setup.

In the following we describe some important key aspects of heterogeneous memory access using GPUs.

5.1 Heterogeneous Memory Systems

5.1.1 Device Memory and Interconnect Study

Device memory on GPUs is usually not flat but itself consists of a hierarchy. In general, one faces large volume memory with slow bandwidth available to all processes (threads) and small volume memory at high bandwidth shared between a smaller group of threads or even memory local to a single thread of very limited volume and very high bandwidth.

Usually, writing in parallel to any of the memories that allow for concurrent access can result in writing conflicts that need to be resolved by the developer. Concurrent reading is not an issue in modern GPUs, but optimized reading in aggregated data chunks still helps to optimize throughput, e.g. by aligning and pitching data structures to fit to the memory lanes of GPU architectures.

In concurrent read/write operations one can either serialize access via atomics or take care of access via explicit synchronization of threads. As an example, before computing the charge density of a number of particles one would take care that all processes (threads) that updated the positions of charges have finished by synchronizing all these threads. Both atomics and synchronization can potentially lead to a reduction in parallelism as they either explicitly serialize executions or create load imbalances as some processes (threads) take longer to finish at a synchronization barrier than others.

Like offloading from CPU to GPU, offloading work from the slow yet large memory accessible by all threads on a GPU to the high bandwidth memory used by a smaller cooperative group of threads must come with an overall increase in throughput of data objects. It is thus essential to understand the design parameters of the different memories present on accelerator hardware.

Concerning host to device memory copies, these can either be managed by explicitly evoking copies, pinning memory on the host to reserve for communication with the GPU or using unified memory access where the developer uses a single memory address space accessible both from host and device and managed by the system. Although unified memory is a powerful and useful tools, manual throughput optimization is still of interest. It critically depends on data layout in memory. The *LLAMA* library introduced below allows to easily switch memory layouts for complex, user-defined C++ data types. It comes with standard layout templates such as array of struct (AoS), struct of array (SoA) or array of struct of array (AoSoA) that can be easily extended by users.

We used *LLAMA* for studying host to device copy speedup based on data layout aware copies. Fig. 19 shows throughput differences for copies depending for typical data layouts compared to various copy strategies, including naive field-wise copies, `std::copy`, all compared to `memcpy` as a baseline. It clearly shows throughput increase when choosing data layout aware copies.

Figure 19: ”Throughput comparison of several copy implementations between different mappings. The particle record dimension consists of seven floats. The event record dimension consists of the first 100 int32s, int64s, floats, bytes, and bools [...]. The (p) versions are parallel. The (r) versions read contiguously, whereas the (w) versions write contiguously. For the field-wise naive and std::copy, the throughput depends a lot on the field types of the record dimension. The aosoa_copy outperforms both of them in most cases, single- and multithreaded”, cited from [10].

For a long time, the CPU-GPU interconnect, connecting the CPU with one or more GPUs, has been a bottleneck in HPC systems, when compared to the memory bandwidth of the CPU and GPUs, and compared to the bandwidth of GPU-GPU interconnects. However, recent hardware changes propose to relax this constraint by providing a high-performance CPU-GPU interconnect, along with a tight integration of CPU and GPU memory spaces. This is the approach chosen for Nvidia’s Grace Hopper Superchip, where one ARM CPU is coupled with an Nvidia H100 GPU, through a 900 GB/s NVLink-C2C “chip-to-chip” interconnect. In addition, fully-hardware features present on both CPU and GPU unify the two physical memory spaces into a single virtual memory space, therefore hiding from the user the complexity of the system. In other terms, this hardware provides a fully hardware-level implementation of Unified Memory, which was previously implemented in major parts as part of the software – driver and runtime. We evaluated this memory system [34], by implementing its use in both a set small-scale benchmarks and state-of-the-art application, representative of diverse memory access patterns.

This memory system is materialized by the fact that memory allocated by the system allocator `malloc` can be located either on CPU or GPU memory, and can be accessed from either of those processors. Fig. 20 presents the result of bandwidth measurements for host-to-device data movements. Explicit data copy with `cudaMemcpy`, achieves up to 85% of the theoretical bandwidth. Direct access from kernel code over the CPU-GPU interconnect, when using system-allocated memory, provides a similar level of performance, showing the viability of direct access and system-allocated memory to use in scientific applications. In the opposite direction, device-to-host, we observed that explicit data movements can exhibit lower bandwidth than direct memory access from kernel code. This reinforces the idea that direct memory access can be an efficient solution to leverage the full bandwidth of the interconnect.

An important aspect visible in this graph is the lack of bandwidth improvement when pinning host memory, compared to regular pageable memory, on a Grace Hopper system. While this is true for sustained bandwidth, it appears that when non-initialized and non-pinned system-allocated memory is accessed from the GPU, performance drops significantly. This is caused by the overhead of page initialization, which is performed on the CPU-side. In this configuration, several GPU threads access non-physically-allocated pages over the interconnect, this triggers page fault, and therefore page fault handling on the CPU-side, causing a high-overhead. In this case, memory pinning can still be proposed as a solution to pre-allocate pages, and avoid this high cost of initialization, with the drawback that pinning will force the page location on the CPU-side, which might not be desirable.

Another aspect essential in the Grace Hopper memory system, which we evaluate, is the automatic counter-based memory migration. As a memory allocation can be located

Figure 20: Host-to-device copy bandwidth for various memory interfaces on a Grace Hopper system, *system* memory indicates the new type of hardware-supported unified memory. Percentage values indicate the achieved bandwidth relative to the theoretical peak.

either on CPU memory, or on GPU memory; when such allocation is heavily accessed by one of those processors, the overhead of access over the CPU-GPU interconnect can hinder performance. Therefore, a software-implemented migration system is in place, to improve locality of frequently remotely-accessed memory regions. In this setup, frequent accesses to a CPU-located 2 MB memory region will trigger migration to GPU memory. Those migrations are shown to be a key asset for application performance, due to the improved locality. However, the operation of migrating memory regions is costly, both in terms of using interconnect bandwidth, which cannot be used for other purposes; and in terms of overhead caused when a region in the process of being migrated is accessed, resulting in potential stalls.

5.1.2 Memory exposure and performance of HBM/DDR

Note: This section is at the intersection with works realized in WP2. Please consider reading deliverable D2.4 for complementary information.

Rhea, the EPI-processor, is designed with two tiers of memory: HBM (High Bandwidth Memory) and DDR (Double Data Rate memory). HBM offers high bandwidth but comes with higher latency and limited capacity. In contrast, DDR provides larger capacity and lower latency but at the expense of bandwidth. This dual-memory architecture is ideal for co-design, allowing developers to allocate critical data to either HBM or DDR based on specific performance requirements.

Effectively utilizing these two memory tiers requires tools that simplify data manipulation, allocation, and migration between HBM and DDR. One potential solution is leveraging existing frameworks, particularly SYCL, an abstraction library that enables seamless management of CPUs and accelerators. SYCL facilitates allocation on devices (via `malloc_device`) or hosts (via `malloc_host`) and provides a unified interface (USM) for transparent memory management across host and device. In Rhea’s context, SYCL could be adapted to manage the dual memory system efficiently.

It has been reported in Delivery D4.2 some experiments to identify the optimal workflow for offloading tasks to the CPU when accelerated resources are unnecessary. Initial findings suggest that AdaptiveCpp is a strong candidate for this purpose. By leveraging SYCL, Rhea could expose a new type of “accelerator” dedicated solely to memory man-

Figure 21: SNC-4 configuration of the Sapphire Rapids

Figure 22: Latency on x86 Sapphire Rapids: DDR (left) and HBM(right)

agement on the CPU. This approach would simplify handling both HBM and DDR while offering a unified framework for CPUs and accelerators. *It is worth noting that SiPearl is also exploring additional frameworks to enhance data handling across memory tiers.*

Memory Exposure and Performance Considerations.

The co-design of Rhea necessitates decisions about how memory is presented to users. The simplest approach is to expose one NUMA node for HBM and one for DDR. However, this abstraction obscures the hardware’s complexity, as multiple memory banks and controllers are aggregated into a single node. This simplification can negatively impact performance, particularly in scalar applications where the HBM targeted may be distant from the core in the Network-on-Chip (NoC). To maximize hardware efficiency, Sapphire Rapids (X86) architecture divides its chip into four quadrants, each paired with one HBM and one DDR. Although the design aggregates the two DDRs per quadrant into a single unit for simplicity (details Fig. 21), this configuration still provides insights into memory performance. For example, Fig. 22 illustrates memory access latency within and across quadrants for both HBM and DDR. Key observations from this architecture include:

- HBM latency is approximately 30% higher than DDR latency.

cores	5	10	20	40
DDR	409 sec	242 sec	136 sec	91 sec
HBM	392 sec	201 sec	115 sec	72 sec
speedup	4%	20%	19%	27%

Table 4: Runtime impact of HBM/DDR for bit_EBC.inp

- Cross-quadrant memory access incurs a 15ns penalty for both HBM and DDR.
- The worst-case penalty arises from accessing memory on the diagonal opposite quadrant, with a latency increase of up to 22%.

These results underscore the importance of binding cores to the corresponding HBM/DDR pair within the same quadrant to achieve optimal performance. Since Rhea’s memory architecture is expected to be similar, this study provides valuable guidance for its co-design and memory exposure strategies.

Early performance impact of HBM/DDR on PLASMA-PEPSC code

Building on the considerations outlined earlier, initial experiments were conducted using two PLASMA-PEPSC codes: BIT1 and Vlasiator.

For BIT1, it’s important to note that the extracted kernels are not ideal candidates for evaluating HBM and DDR performance. This is because these kernels are purely sequential, meaning they inherently favor DDR for two main reasons: (1) a single core cannot saturate the bandwidth of either HBM or DDR, and (2) DDR offers better latency. As a result, the experiments were carried out directly on the full BIT1 code.

Consequently experiments have been performed directly on the BIT1 code. Table 4 summarizes the results of these experiments. The data shows that BIT1 achieves greater speedup as more cores are utilized: this highlights the benefits of using HBM for bandwidth bounded code. However, significant variability was observed during the tests, and further investigation is needed to understand the causes of this variability.

For Vlasiator, Fig. 23 and Fig. 24 show the initial experiments conducted for both Magnetosphere_3D_small and Ionosphere_small test cases.

In both cases, the configuration of 80 MPI / 1 OMP delivers the best speedup, achieving around 30%. However, switching to a configuration of 1 MPI / 80 OMP significantly improves overall performance, effectively eliminating the benefit of HBM. Additional experiments using more (hyper) threads followed this approach but failed to further enhance HBM’s performance gains.

Detailed profiling revealed that the initial configuration uses twice as much memory as the alternative configuration. This increased memory usage transforms the test cases into bandwidth-bound scenarios. As a result, further investigations at larger scales are required.

While evaluating these benchmarks, we also assessed the performance of the SYCL framework (see Delivery 2.4) on the HecBench benchmark. In this study, we compared the speedup achieved using HBM against DDR memory across 22 benchmarks that are compatible with all frameworks, ensuring consistency in comparison. All benchmarks

Figure 23: Impact of high bandwidth memory, presented as speedup for various MPI/OpenMP configurations on the Ionosphere small test case

Figure 24: Impact of high bandwidth memory, presented as speedup for various MPI/OpenMP configurations on the Magnetosphere small test case

Framework	Minimum	Median	Mean	Maximum
OMPTarget	43%	101%	108%	303%
ACPP omp,accelerated	83%	100%	116%	313%
ACPP omp,library-only	92%	100%	108%	190%
ACPP SSCP omp	92%	100%	117%	334%
ACPP SSCP PoCL	92%	101%	116%	320%
DPC++ PoCL	80%	101%	111%	247%
DPC++ Native CPU	78%	99%	104%	169%

Table 5: Speedup thanks to the HBM on various SYCL backend, targetting CPU, over a subset of 22 benchmarks coming from HecBenchmark

were executed using 20 cores on Sapphire Rapids, which corresponds to the saturation point of the Stream bandwidth microbenchmark for this architecture. The results are summarized in Table 5.

Several observations can be made from these results. First, certain benchmarks, notably the cross benchmark (a cross product of two 2D tensors), achieved an impressive 3x speedup. However, the AdaptiveCpp/LibOnly framework did not reach this level of performance. A closer examination of this framework revealed the use of `nd_range`, which is strongly discouraged for this particular framework.

At the opposite end of the spectrum, there was significant performance degradation observed for OMP-Target. Upon closer analysis, the affected benchmark was identified as `atomicReduction`, which repeatedly performs reductions in an atomic fashion. This highlighted the impact of latency, which is better managed by DDR in this case.

Lastly, the overall performance gain was relatively modest on average. This is primarily because the HecBench suite is designed for general-purpose benchmarking, rather than being optimized for bandwidth- or compute-bound kernels.

Next Steps: This detailed analysis of Sapphire Rapids, along with the initial results, provides promising insights into the effects of NUMA exposure and MPI placement. SiPearl plans to refine these findings and develop more effective tools to optimize memory tiering and MPI placement, improving overall performance.

5.1.3 GPUDirect Storage

Similar to remote direct data access that avoids routing memory copies between two GPUs through the host memory bus, GPUDirect Storage enables direct access to the file system without going through the CPU. In general, these operations are implemented by I/O libraries rather than directly by simulation code. One of the reasons for this is that the solutions are vendor-specific and thus not portable and optimization for a certain parallel file system can be cumbersome. The openPMD API for example mainly utilizes this via its back ends such as HDF5, as it does for GPUDirect RDMA for streaming in-memory workflows.

5.2 Programming Interfaces for in-memory data Management in HMS

In the following we focus on some solutions for in-memory data management of heterogeneous memory that work on different levels of the memory hierarchy. The list is neither complete nor exhaustive but covers various approaches towards managing heterogeneous memory management at varying complexity. The challenge is that vendor-specific solutions for memory management often do not perform well enough to be used for dynamical memory allocation during the simulation, especially for small object allocation. Moreover, memory handling can differ between vendors, thus abstractions that hide this complexity and can provide efficient allocation schemes are of big interest. We list a few approaches followed in PlasmaPEPSC below.

5.2.1 Concurrent memory allocation with *mallocMC*

mallocMC is a policy-based C++ software framework developed by HZDR providing efficient, scalable and configurable on-device dynamic memory allocations orders of magnitude faster than what the vendor's native implementations typically provide. The need for this kind of software is particularly high in PIC simulations where large numbers of particles are created, destroyed and moved around in every time step. Each particle being a small datum, the highly concurrent access to GPU memory being a shared resource brings challenges unseen on CPU. Consequently, standard CPU approaches to this problem cannot be ported and new algorithms have to be developed.

Figure 25: *mallocMC* speed-up of one representative pattern of single-size allocations on an NVIDIA A30 as well as AMD Threadripper 1950X CPU compared to the vendor-native allocator. Larger is better. Please note the logarithmic axis. One sees that the AMD allocator performs better than the Nvidia one, while *mallocMC* provides either comparable or orders of magnitude better.

mallocMC is maintained and developed as part of PLASMA-PEPSC in a completely open source fashion on Github.¹ In the latest iteration, it provides three different algorithms (plus the option for user-defined algorithms) for managing on-device memory within a kernel as well as configurable infrastructure around it. Preliminary benchmarks suggest a speed-up of up to 300x compared to native allocations on an NVIDIA A30

¹<https://github.com/alpaka-group/mallocMC>

as can be seen in 25. A more thorough evaluation of its performance is under way. Its design makes it easy to maintain and extend such that keeping up with improvements on hardware and software side is fostered making it a future-proof and sustainable library to build on. At the time of writing, it has been powering PIconGPU for more than a decade already.

While there is certainly some overlap of applicability, it should be stressed that `mal-locMC` is on a significantly lower abstraction level than other solutions discussed here. For example, Umpire provides much higher-level memory management abstractions. `mal-locMC` would rather correspond to a particular form of pool in Umpire.

5.2.2 Optimum memory layout and reduced representations with Llama

Figure 26: *LLAMA*-provided mapping from user-defined data types (left) to an abstract index space (center) to a data layout in memory (right), from [10].

LLAMA, the library for Low-Level Abstraction of Memory Access, breaks with the C++ convention that the structure of a data type defines its layout in memory. While this paradigm had already been weakened by the introduction of the standard template library in C++, where data structure access and internal representation were partially disentangled, *LLAMA* uses standard C++ techniques to install a general, multi-dimensional index space that maps user-defined data types to this index space and maps this index space to a specific layout in memory, see Fig. 26.

Examples for standard mappings already included in *LLAMA* are, array of struct, struct of array, array of struct of array. In addition, *LLAMA* provides user-defined mappings, working both at compile and run time. For mixed precision, mappings to reduced precision representations exist. Once data structures in code are annotated by *LLAMA*, switching to a given data layout is a matter of changing a single line of code.

LLAMA was developed by HZDR together with *CERN* and *Technical University Dresden* and works independently of *alpaka* but is well suited for use together with *alpaka*, as *alpaka* maps processes to an abstract index space, making data parallel access equivalent to an index mapping operation.

5.2.3 H2M

H2M is a flexible, portable approach that works across different vendors and technologies to help manage data placement in systems with diverse types of memory. It allows programmers to specify requirements or provide hints—referred to as traits in the paper—about how data is accessed and used. The library uses these hints to efficiently allocate data across the available memory subsystems and can even move data dynamically at runtime. Additionally, they provide monitoring tools to make easier for programmers to choose the right traits for each piece of data by automatically generating memory access profiles and analyzing how data behaves, offering tailored recommendations for requirements or hints.

While this library is suitable for early experiments, its flexibility and portable architecture come with the cost of storing each memory allocation on a single page. Consequently, this approach lacks of scalability and is underefficient in term of memory usage. Also this flexibility requires a lot of locking schemes on shared data-structures that alters performance.

As a consequence, SiPearl is working on a more suited approach, combined with compiler directives that falls back into dedicated memory management library. Additionally, next step would be to have a look to UMF, a memory management framework provided by the oneAPI suite.

5.2.4 StarPU

StarPU framework is a C++ wrapper that allows different "codelets" to be implemented for heterogeneous architectures (EPI, RISC-V, FPGA, GPU) and run as tasks with data-dependency awareness. Extracted kernels from work package 2 (WP2) can thus be implemented in an optimal way using dedicated compiler/language selection and specific optimisations. Calibration of codelets for performance models provide sizing of the buffers and timing under selected scheduling strategy. The main challenge in codelet design stays with data locality breakdown (cache coherency) for memory transfer between tasks and inter-node dependencies. Most of the StarPU development has been done with BIT1 code base for which memory reorganisation is underway.

5.2.5 Umpire

Vlasiator and the Hashinator library [29, 30] are in the process of being ported to support memory allocation using the Umpire [6] portable allocation interface. Future work will allow a wider variety of memory allocators to be implemented.

6 Conclusion

This report details strategies of porting Plasma-PEPSC codes to accelerator devices with a strong focus on GPUs. Various strategies, from accelerating critical paths in the codes to using high-level libraries such as *GTENSOR* or cross-platform parallel programming libraries such as *alpaka* are discussed. Particular emphasis is put on accelerator memory allocation, as vendor-specific solutions can be slow. Significant progress has been made across all Plasma-PEPSC codes in adapting to high-performance heterogeneous

computing systems. BIT1 porting to hybrid MPI and OpenMP/OpenACC frameworks has progressed significantly, achieving notable performance improvements and scalability on EuroHPC systems, with future efforts focusing on reducing GPU-CPU data transfer bottlenecks and exploring CUDA streams and hybrid approaches. GENE has reached production readiness with *GTENSOR*, while GENE-X has implemented GPU offloading for time integration, achieving substantial runtime reductions. Both codes continue to optimize AMD GPU performance, address field solver challenges, and prepare for large-scale ITER simulations. PIconGPU has demonstrated strong scaling on platforms like LUMI and JUWELS BOOSTER through the alpaka library and enhanced memory management with mallocMC. Future efforts aim to explore using matrix processing units, and improve exascale performance with tests on JUPITER. Vlasiator has transitioned its Vlasov solver and memory structures to GPUs, enhancing stability and efficiency, though challenges remain in closing the performance gap between NVIDIA and AMD hardware. Work is on track to ensure the codes are well-prepared for the demands of exascale computing. We note that the project requires testing on systems that resemble the upcoming exascale systems to verify the results of research on the cutting-edge hardware. The project therefore would greatly benefit from the availability of the corresponding resources.

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